

THE COMPARISON OF NARCISSISM SCORES OF FEMALE ATHLETES IN DIFFERENT BRANCHES

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Abstract:

This study aims to compare narcissism levels of female athletes in different branches. The narcissism levels of students who voluntarily agreed to participate in the study have been measured through 16-question Narcissistic Personality Inventory (NPI-16) which has been coordinated by Daniel R. Ames, Paul Rose and Cameron P. Anderson in 2005. The validity and the reliability of the Inventory have been done by Salim ATAY in 2009. For analyses of the data, Portable IBM SPSS Statistics v20 software package was used. The descriptive analysis, one-way Anova analysis which was used to determine the difference between two variances and Tukey's test were also used in data analysis. At the end of the study, it was observed that the narcissism score of bodybuilding athletes is higher than other athletes in the scope of the study.

Keywords: narcissism, female athlete, compare

1. Introduction

Narcissistic personality is defined as the person who admires his physical and psychological characteristics and is so much full of himself (Güney, 1998: 198, Hançerlioğlu, 1993: 258).

According to Freud, he describes narcissism as libidinal investment from the outside world by pulling one's self-directed and he talks about two kinds of narcissism. Primary narcissism is described as the child's libidinal investment in external objects, not of self-directed and that all children have to go through such a specific maturation process. According to Freud, primary narcissism and libidinal energy are found in self/ego from the start and they are not directed to the objects. This situation is followed

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by swelling of the self-accompanied by feelings of being powerful and precise. Freud also defined secondary narcissism as relationship difficulties and frustrations as a result of acts of the next process, which is made of the libidinal investment in the outside World and withdrawing from people, directed to self/ego (Geçtan, 2004:254).

Narcissistic athletes are the people who admire themselves physically and mentally, see themselves above, expect continuous appreciation, interest and approval, they will meet exclusive of interest wherever they go and think that they deserve the superior place. Such intense narcissistic injuries and disappointments in expectations is also often the inevitable reality. Narcissistic self-esteem of individuals is fed from outside interests, tastes, approvals. People in question cannot stand criticisms and anticipate for constant praises. For this reason, their appearances and manners are formed to grasp all these. Since they make use of the others for glorifying, seem to be superior and reveal themselves; their friendships are just to get benefit from the others in this way. Narcissistic athletes are known as selfish, egocentric since they do not show empathy towards emotions, thoughts and needs of others (Tazegül, 2013e).

Narcissism may sometimes affect the performance of the athletes positively. Narcissistic athletes themselves feel valuable, and their admiration for others to gain advantage depends on the capabilities of reveal themselves. They reveal their superiority by exhibiting the best movements that they perform in the sports field and try to attract attention. They are less interested in being loved and cared when compared to other people. Therefore, narcissistic athletes behave combatant and self-assertive during the competition in order to avoid the destruction of their self-esteem due to performance failure. The most important thing for a narcissistic athlete is to win. They also apply for unethical behaviours in order to acquire the targeted objective (Wallace & Baumeister, 2002).

2. Material and Method

2.1 The Sample

The sample group of the study was composed of a total of 98 athletes who voluntarily participated in the study and have professional careers in sports like volleyball, basketball, karate, bodybuilding and tennis.

2.2 Research Data Collection

Narcissistic Personality Inventory composed of 16 questions and translated into Turkish by Salim Atay in 2009 was used as a scale factor. NPI composed of 16 questions was arranged by Daniel R. Ames, Paul Rose ve Cameron P. Anderson in 2005 translated into Turkish by Salim Atay. After the pilot application by Atay Cronbach's Alpha value was

determined as 0,57 in the first performed study. Reliability coefficient below the values expected due to the presence of each factor scale, the negative correlation is detected and evaluated and determined not provide additive scale of four, were revised statement. After the measurements performed this change Cronbach's Alpha value was raised to 0,652. The questions in 16 questions scale factor translated into Turkish by Atay also distributed in 6 factors as superiority, authority, pretension, self-sufficiency and exploitation similar to the 16 questions NPI English version. The points that can be gained from NPI are: extent of authority 0-2, extent of exhibitionism 0-3, extent of exploration 0-3, extent of pretension 0-2, extent of self-sufficiency 0-3, extent of superiority 0-3, total narcissism is between 0-16 points. As the point increases the level of narcissism also increases (Atay, 2010).

2.4 The Analysis of Data

For analyses of the data, SPSS Statistics v20 software package was used. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test was applied in order to decide whether data has normal distribution and it is observed that data has a normal distribution. One-Way ANOVA-Homogeneity of Variance was applied to test the homogeneity of variances and it is also observed that data is homogeneous. After the earlier analysis, it was decided to use parametric test methods for statistical analysis. The descriptive analysis, one-way Anova analysis which was used to determine the difference between two variances and Tukey's test were also used in data analysis.

2.5 Findings

Table 1: The Findings of Descriptive Analysis

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Taekwondo	40	7,4000	3,29426	,39374
Athleticism	35	7,9333	4,58984	1,18509
Bodybuilding	32	12,6667	,51640	,21082
Volleyball	33	9,3333	4,41760	1,27525
Basketball	40	7,7273	3,12800	,47156
Tennis	36	9,0000	3,62531	1,28174

According to the results of descriptive statistical analysis, narcissism scores of taekwondo players as (7,4000±3, 3,29426), athletes as (7,9333±3, 4,58984), bodybuilding athletes as (12,6667±,51640), volleyball players as (9,3333±,4,41760), basketball players as (7,7273±,3,12800) and tennis players (7,7273±,3,12800).

Table 2: The result of one-way analysis of variance

	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	188,481	37,696	3,169	,010
Within Groups	1772,461	11,896		

According to the analysis of variance, statistically significant difference was found between narcissism levels of female athletes and the variance of their branches.

Table 3: The result of Tukey's test

		Mean Difference	Std. Error	Sig.
Taekwondo	Bodybuilding	-5,26667*	1,46716	,000
Athleticism	Bodybuilding	-4,73333*	1,66603	,005
Bodybuilding	Taekwondo	5,26667*	1,46716	,000
	Athleticism	4,73333*	1,66603	,005
	Volleyball	3,33333	1,72451	,055
	Basketball	4,93939*	1,50099	,001
	Tennis	3,66667	1,86268	,051

According to the result of Tukey's test, statistically differences were found between taekwondo and bodybuilding branches, basketball and bodybuilding branches, bodybuilding branch and taekwondo and athletics branches.

3. Discussion and Conclusion

The result of descriptive statistical analysis indicated that the narcissism score of bodybuilding athletes is higher than other athletes in the scope of this study. According to the comparison of the branches in the study, statistically significant differences were found between bodybuilding and taekwondo branches, bodybuilding and basketball branches and bodybuilding and athletics branches. The narcissism score of bodybuilding athletes is higher than other athletes in the scope of the study and it is considered normal, because one of the important features of the narcissistic personality is that narcissistic people excessively admire and like their bodies. Bodybuilding athletes usually have good-physical and ideal body and so, the situation that narcissism score of bodybuilding athletes is higher than other athletes in the scope of the study is considered normal. If this result is evaluated considering narcissistic person identity, it is commented that bodybuilding athletes highly admire their personal and physical abilities in compare to other athletes in the scope of the study. According to literature research carried out, some studies in parallel with the study data were compared.

Tazegül and Güven (2015) reveal that narcissism score of bodybuilding athletes is higher than other athletes in boxing, wrestling, weightlifting, athletics, swimming, basketball, karate and football branches and individuals who are not engaged in sports. Klein (1987) claimed that no one can be more narcissistic than athletes engaged in bodybuilding branches. Klein also indicated that bodybuilding athletes always tend to make a great display with their aesthetic physics. Many studies reveal that narcissistic people give a lot of importance to their appearances.

Emmons (1984) reveal that narcissists exceedingly give the importance to their appearances and they extremely motivate through when they achieve good physical appearance. Jackson and et al. (1992) and Davis and et al. (2001) found that narcissists are extremely obsessed with their appearances. Davis (1992) reported that narcissistic individuals significantly focus on their body appearances and exercise is considered as a mean on this. Davis and et al. (1995) found that high level of narcissism is related with good body image.

According to literature research carried out, some studies in parallel with the study data were found. Some of these studies were given below:

Tazegül (2013) reveal the relationship between narcissism score and self-esteem of female badminton players and at the end of the study, positive correlation was found between athletes' narcissism and self-esteem scores. Tazegül (2013a) determined weightlifters' narcissism level as (7.283 ± 2.786) and boxers as (7.216 ± 2.584) . Tazegül (2013b) found that there is a positive relationship between boxers' narcissism and motivation orientation. Tazegül et al. (2013c) determined wrestlers' narcissism level (6.707 ± 2.775) . Tazegül (2013a) found a positive correlation between Greco-Roman wrestlers' sports age and narcissism scores. Tazegül (2012) compared narcissism levels of 4-5 and 6-8 years of sports age for freestyle wrestlers and found statistically significant difference. Tazegül and Soykan (2013d) observed that narcissism scores of athletes for 16 age group are higher than narcissism scores of athletes for 17 and 18 age group and narcissism scores of 8 years and older of sports age for athletes are also higher than narcissism scores of 8 years and older of sports age for athletes.

Gezer (2014) found narcissism level of students at the School of Physical Education and Sports of Mustafa Kemal University as 6.83. Elman et al. (2003) determined narcissism levels of football players as 19.4, basketball and rugby players as 17.8 and individuals who are not engaged in sports as 15.2. Athletes are more narcissistic than individuals who are not engaged in sports, so the most important reason is that athletes are thought that they have nice and aesthetic appearance. Sohrabi et al. (2011) compared the narcissism levels of athletes engaged in in-contact sports (boxing and karate) and non-contact sports (swimming and gymnastics) and statistically significant difference was found. Arthur et al. (2011) found narcissism level

of coaches as 13.37. Tschanz and et al (1998) reported that men are more narcissistic than women. Tammy et al (2007) found that men are more narcissistic than women. Stankiewicz and Pawłowska (2010) reveal that narcissism levels of women who do regularly exercises are higher than individuals who are not athlete.

As a result, the narcissism score of female athletes engaged in bodybuilding branch which significantly requires physical development is higher than other athletes in the scope of this study. This result is considered normal. Because narcissistic personality is that narcissistic people excessively admire and like their bodies and give importance their developments. Therefore, it is considered normal that the narcissism score of female bodybuilding athletes is higher than other athletes in the scope of this study.

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